

A Review and Discussion of the Mean – Median Protocol Acceptability of Data and Reporting Test Result as Arithmetic Mean

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ABSTRACT

The testing laboratories , often , expressed their final quoted test result as arithmetic mean of replicate measurements . Whether all the data obtained during the replicate measurements are correct and can be used for calculating arithmetic mean ? , yet under noticed . This article describes and exemplifies the Mean – Median method for determining the acceptability of data , applicable for reporting of test result as arithmetic mean or median , the measurement uncertainty , verification and validation of test methods and for defining acceptability criteria for replicate measurements in quality control activities .

KEYWORDS

Arithmetic Mean , Precision , Median , Replicate , Range , Critical Range factor , outlier , verification , validation , uncertainty

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INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of data obtained during replicate measurements is of great importance to a number of laboratory activities . The arithmetic mean of such data is used for reporting test results , calculating measurement uncertainty , defining criteria for replicate measurements and as specification in validation and verification of test methods .

The acceptability , accuracy and validity of test result is of great importance as it is an embodiment of the competence of a laboratory . The laboratories have a general thinking that if the result of test parameter is expressed as arithmetic mean of two or more replicates , error can be minimised and the result becomes more accurate . Is it correct ? . Whether arithmetic mean is the only solution ? . No lab personnel is bothered about it and yet the question remains under discussed .

In our opinion , merely expressing the test result as arithmetic mean is totally wrong . The collected data has to be evaluated before reporting the value . The result can be expressed as either arithmetic mean or median . When and where the arithmetic mean or median is used for expressing test result can be determined by a number of international methods .

Through this article , we made an earnest attempt to discuss the procedure based on Mean – Median method for evaluating the data of replicate measurements and expressing the result as either arithmetic mean or median . The protocol is well illustrated and hypothesis are used at certain places .

DEFINITION

Some important definitions are included .

1. Precision : The closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained under stipulated conditions . Repeatability and reproducibility are particular sets of extreme conditions
2. Independent test results : Means results obtained in a manner not influenced by any previous result on the same or similar test object.
3. Repeatability : Precision under repeatability condition
4. Repeatability Condition : Conditions where independent test results are obtained with same method on identical test items in the same laboratory by the same operator using the same equipment within short intervals of time .
5. Criteria : A set of requirements used as a reference against which objective evidence is compared .
6. Arithmetic Mean : The sum of a collection of numbers divided by the count of the numbers in the collection . It is simply called mean or Average and is the Central value of data set .
7. Median : The middle value in a data set that has been arranged in ascending or descending order .
8. Standard Deviation : The amount of variation or dispersion in a data set , showing how much the individual data points typically deviate form the mean .
9. Outlier : A member of a set of values which is inconsistent with the other members of that set .

ABBREVIATION

- 1) ISO – International organisation for Standardisation
- 2) IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission
- 3) SD – Standard Deviation
- 4) CR – Critical Range
- 5) r – Repeatability Limit

DESCRIPTION OF METHODOLOGY

The International Standard for the competency of testing , ISO/IEC 17025 requires that laboratory has to generate valid test results . The validity of test results can be ensured by internal as well as external quality control activities .

The laboratory personnel usually perform replicate analysis , called repeatability , as an internal quality control activity , but never evaluate the data before the final result is being reported . This will , some times , cause reporting of incorrect test results . The acceptability of arithmetic mean can be checked by a number of international methods . Here , we discuss , the Mean – Median protocol with real data evaluation .

The protocol uses a new terminology , called **Critical Range Factor , $f(n)$** , which is the 95% quantile of the distribution of $(X_{max} - X_{min})/\sigma$ where X_{max} and X_{min} are the extreme values in a sample of size n from a normal distribution with standard deviation σ . The critical values are given in Table – 1 .

The Critical Range Factor is , then , used to calculate **Critical Range (CR_{0.95(n)})** , according to the equation

$$CR_{0.95(n)} = f(n) \cdot \sigma$$

Remember , **critical range** and **range** are two different terminology , where the latter is the difference between two extreme results , **X_{max}** and **X_{min}** .

If only two replicate data are obtained , the comparison is made with **Repeatability limit (r)** , according to the equation

$$r = 2.8 \sigma$$

Table – 1

Where **f(n)** – critical range factor and **n** – number of replicates , where **n ≥ 5**

n	f(n)										
2	2.8	10	4.5	18	4.9	26	5.2	34	5.4	50	5.6
3	3.3	11	4.6	19	5.0	27	5.2	35	5.4	60	5.8
4	3.6	12	4.6	20	5.0	28	5.3	36	5.4	70	5.9
5	3.9	13	4.7	21	5.0	29	5.3	37	5.4	80	5.9
6	4.0	14	4.7	22	5.1	30	5.3	38	5.5	90	6.0
7	4.2	15	4.8	23	5.1	31	5.3	39	5.5	100	6.1
8	4.3	16	4.8	24	5.1	32	5.3	40	5.5	-----	-----
9	4.3	17	4.9	25	5.2	33	5.4	45	5.6	-----	-----

DISCUSSION

Two schemes , based on Mean – Median protocol , with scenario are discussed with examples : Hypothetical values are used at some places of standard deviation .

Scenario – 1 : Two replicates

The following scheme can be used to evaluate two replicate tests .

1. Calculate the arithmetic mean , standard deviation , absolute difference and repeatability limit .
2. If the absolute difference does not exceed repeatability limit , then both test results are considered acceptable, and the final quoted result should be quoted as the arithmetic mean of the two test results .
3. If the absolute difference does exceed repeatability limit , the laboratory should obtain two further test results .
4. Arrange the four test results in ascending/descending order
5. If the range (**X_{max} – X_{min}**) of the four test results is equal to or less than the critical range for **n = 4** , **CR_{0.95(4)}**, the arithmetic mean of the four test results should be reported as the final quoted result .
6. If the range of the four test results is greater than the critical range for **n = 4**, the median of the four test results should be reported as the final quoted result .

The two situations are exemplified in Table – 2 and Table – 3

Table – 2 (Two test results are acceptable)

Test Parameter	Saponification Value of Coconut Oil
Data (2 Replicates)	251.72 , 252.84
Arithmetic Mean	252.28
Standard Deviation σ	0.56
Repeatability Range	$2.8 \times 0.56 = 1.568$
Absolute Difference	$252.84 - 251.72 = 1.12$
Remarks	Since absolute difference does not exceed repeatability range , both data are acceptable The final quoted result = 252.28

Table – 3 (Two test results are insufficient)

Test Parameter	Total Hardness of Drinking Water (mg/l)
Data (2 Replicates)	47.58 , 48.09 with stated standard deviation of 0.16
Mean	47.835
Standard Deviation σ	0.16 (stated)
Repeatability Range	$2.8 \times 0.16 = 0.448$
Absolute Difference	$48.09 - 47.58 = 0.51$
Remarks – 1	Since absolute difference exceeds repeatability range , data are not acceptable . Obtain two more test results , 47.77 , 48.21
Test Results Descending Order	48.21 , 48.09 , 47.77 , 47.58
Mean (4 replicates)	47.9125
Standard Deviation σ	0.2504
Critical Range $CR_{0.95}(4)$	$3.6 \times 0.2504 = 0.9014$
Range	$48.21 - 47.58 = 0.63$
Remarks – 2	Since the range does not exceed critical range , all the four data are acceptable and the arithmetic mean of data is reported as the final quoted result Mean = 47.835 mg/l

Scenario – 2 : Replicate Analysis where $n \geq 5$

When a sufficiently large number ($n \geq 5$) of test results are obtained under repeatability conditions

1. Record n replicate data , such that $n \geq 5$ and arrange in ascending/descending order
2. Calculate the arithmetic mean , standard deviation , range and Critical Range
3. If the range does not exceed the critical range , then the arithmetic mean of all the n test results is reported as the final quoted result .
4. If the range exceeds the critical range , further measurements is required . The number of further
5. measurement , say m , will depends on the size of n and the ease of performing the

- measurements . **m** has to be chosen as an integer satisfying the condition $n/3 \leq m \leq n/2$
- If the range of all the $n+m$ results not exceed the critical range , **CR0.95(n+m)** , then the arithmetic mean of all the $n+m$ test results is reported as the final quoted result .
 - If the range exceeds the critical range , **Median** of all (**n+m**) result is quoted as the final test result .

The three situations are exemplified in Table – 4 , Table – 5 and Table – 6

Table – 4 (Initial data sufficient)

Test	Curcumin content (mg/l) in Turmeric Powder
Data (12 Replicates) Ascending Order	3.09 , 3.14 , 3.36 , 3.61 , 3.72 , 3.93 , 4.05 , 4.15 , 4.19 , 4.28 , 4.86 , 5.17
Mean	3.9875
Standard Deviation	0.6055
Critical range CR0.95(12)	$4.6 \times 0.6055 = 2.7853$
Range	$5.17 - 3.09 = 2.08$
Remarks	Since the range does not exceed critical range , all data are acceptable and the arithmetic mean of data is reported as the final quoted result Mean = 3.9875 mg/l

Table – 5 (Initial Data insufficient – Quoted Result as Mean)

Test	Tartrazine Colour(mg/l) in Fruit Drink
Data (9 Replicates)	75.98 , 75.46 , 75.06 , 74.79 , 74.35 , 74.13 , 73.91 , 72.97 , 72.39
Ascending Order	
Mean	74.338
Standard Deviation	0.58 (stated)
CriticalRange CR0.95(9)	$4.4 \times 0.58 = 2.552$
Range	$75.98 - 72.39 = 3.59$
Remarks – 1	Since the range of 9 test results exceeds critical range , data are not acceptable . Obtain more Data , such that $n/3 \leq m \leq n/2 = 9/3 \leq m \leq 9/2 = 3 \leq m \leq 4.5$ Thus 3 or 4 tests can be performed . Collect 3 more data (m=3) 73.91 , 75.06 , 74.88
Data Ascending order	75.98 , 75.46 , 75.06 , 75.06 , 74.88 , 74.79 , 74.35 , 74.13 , 73.91 , 73.91 , 72.97 , 72.39
Mean (9+3 Replicates)	74.4075
Standard Deviation	0.98
CriticalRange CR0.95(12)	$4.6 \times 0.98 = 4.508$
Range	$75.98 - 72.39 = 3.59$
Remarks – 2	Since the range of 12 test results does not exceed critical range , all data are acceptable and the arithmetic mean of data is reported as the final quoted result Mean = 74.4075 mg/l

Table – 6 (All Data insufficient - Quoted Result as Median)

Test	Protein Content (mg/l) in Nutrimix
Data (6 Replicates) Ascending Order	15.41 , 15.72 , 15.92 , 16.64 , 16.93 , 17.18
Mean	16.2957
Standard Deviation	0.43 (stated)
Critical Range CR0.95(6)	$4.0 \times 0.43 = 1.72$
Range	$17.18 - 15.41 = 1.77$
Remarks – 1	Since the range of 6 test results exceeds critical range , data are not acceptable . Obtain more data such that $n/3 \leq m \leq n/2 = 6/3 \leq m \leq 6/2 = 2 \leq m \leq 3$ Thus 2 or 3 tests can be performed . Collect 3 more data (m=3) 16.57 , 15.93 , 16.84
Data (9 Replicates) Descending order	17.18 , 16.93 , 16.84 , 16.64 , 16.57 , 15.93 , 15.92 , 15.72 , 15.41
Mean	16.349
Standard Deviation	0.39 (Stated)
Critical Range CR0.95(9)	$4.4 \times 0.39 = 1.716$
Range	$17.18 - 15.41 = 1.77$
Remarks – 2	Range of all the 9 test results exceeds critical range , Arithmetic mean can't be used . Median of data is reported as final quoted result . Median = 16.57 mg/l

CONCLUSION

The Mean – Median method for the acceptability of data is well illustrated by examples . The testing laboratories can follow this method to evaluate data where the final result is reported as arithmetic mean . The evaluation is equally beneficial for calculating measurement uncertainty , verification and validation of test methods and defining acceptability criteria for replicate measurements in internal quality control activities .

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Notes

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